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The Pros and Cons of a Cesarean Section.

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Abstract: A Caesarean section (CS) is the surgical delivery of the fetus and placenta. It is important for every woman to understand the pros and cons of this procedure, as this form of childbirth is becoming more common despite WHO recommendations for vaginal birth. This article presents the pros, cons, indications, and contraindications of cesarean sections. Research data from Russian-language literature searches in cyberleninka.ru, eLIBRARY, and Scopus international databases for the period 2020-2025 were processed and analyzed.

Keywords: Caesarean section, childbirth, pregnancy, indications, contraindications, and complications.

Introduction

A cesarean section is a surgical procedure for delivery in which the fetus and placenta are removed through an incision made in the uterus. According to WHO data, the cesarean section rate ranges from 10% to 15% in economically developed countries. In some maternity hospitals in Russia, it has reached 30–40% or higher and continues to rise. According to the global literature, one in four women gives birth via cesarean section, and one in five of them experiences complications during the postoperative period. It is important to note that the gestational age for performing an elective cesarean section is after 39 weeks of pregnancy, as the risk of respiratory complications in infants is significantly reduced [2]. For a cesarean section, the ideal method of pain relief is regional anesthesia—spinal or epidural. General anesthesia is necessary only in the most urgent cases. The decision regarding the choice of anesthesia method is made by the woman herself, as every type of anesthesia has its own advantages and disadvantages, as well as side effects [3].

Indications

To standardize the indications for cesarean section, it is advisable to divide them into three main groups: indications for elective cesarean section during pregnancy; indications for emergency cesarean section during pregnancy; and indications for cesarean section during labor.

Indications for elective cesarean section during pregnancy: placenta previa;

- placenta accreta;
- uterine scar insufficiency (following a cesarean section, myomectomy, uterine perforation, removal of a rudimentary horn, or excision of the uterine corner during an ectopic pregnancy);
- uterine scar following three or more cesarean sections;
- obstacles in the birth canal preventing delivery (anatomically narrow pelvis with a narrowing of grade II or higher, pelvic bone deformities, tumors of the uterus, ovaries, or pelvic organs);
- severe symphysis pubis diastasis;
- estimated fetal weight of 4,500 g or more;

- severe scar deformities of the cervix and vagina;
- history of plastic surgery on the cervix or vagina, repair of urogenital or enterogenital fistulas, or third-degree cervical or perineal lacerations;
- Breech presentation combined with a fetal weight >3800 g
- Extragenital conditions leading to a deterioration in the pregnant woman's condition;
- Agony or sudden death of the woman while the fetus is still alive.

Indications for emergency cesarean section during labor

During labor, the indications for cesarean section are the same as during pregnancy. In addition, a cesarean section may become necessary in the event of the following labor complications:

- uncorrectable uterine contractile dysfunction (weakness, dyscoordination);
- clinically narrow pelvis;
- prolapse of a pulsating umbilical cord loop and/or small fetal parts in cephalic presentation;
- breech presentation.

Can a doctor decide to deliver the baby vaginally if there are indications for a cesarean section? Yes, but in doing so, the doctor bears moral and, in some cases, legal responsibility in the event of an adverse outcome for the mother and fetus. If there are indications for a cesarean section during pregnancy, it is preferable to perform the procedure on a scheduled basis, as it has been proven that the number of complications for the mother and child is significantly lower than in cases of emergency interventions. An elective cesarean section cannot prevent the negative effects of antenatal factors leading to the development of hypoxia or infection in the fetus. In addition, a violation of the surgical technique for performing a cesarean section (insufficient incision in the uterus, etc.) can lead to trauma to the fetus during its extraction.

A cesarean section may also be performed based on a combination of indications, none of which individually constitutes a basis for performing a cesarean section, but together they pose a real threat to the fetus's health in the event of vaginal delivery. These include a combination of post-term pregnancy and unprepared birth canal, a primiparous woman over 35 years of age and a large fetus, or a history of prolonged infertility and breech presentation, etc. [1].

Currently, there is a global debate regarding elective cesarean sections performed at a woman's request for various reasons (fear of injury to the baby during childbirth, reluctance to experience pain during labor, or changes in the anatomy and function of the reproductive organs following previous spontaneous deliveries). It is essential to explain to patients the benefits and advantages of vaginal delivery; the physician must make every effort to avoid performing a cesarean section at the woman's request. If there are relative indications that could, with some degree of probability, lead to an adverse outcome during vaginal delivery, the physician must agree to perform a cesarean section.

Identifying contraindications and conditions for operative delivery plays a crucial role in the outcome of a cesarean section for both the mother and the fetus.

Contraindications

- 1) intrauterine fetal death or a malformation incompatible with life;
- 2) fetal hypoxia in the absence of urgent maternal indications, if there is no certainty that a live (single heartbeat) and viable infant will be born

In cases of vital maternal indications, the listed contraindications are disregarded [1].

The Pros and Cons of Cesarean Sections

Vaginal delivery has always been considered the preferred method of childbirth. However, a cesarean section may be performed for medical reasons related to complications during pregnancy and/or simply at the request of the pregnant woman. The excessive promotion of cesarean sections in recent decades has created a false impression among people that this method of delivery is safe and causes fewer postpartum complications for both the mother and the baby. However, the opposite is true. Some studies show that the risk of complications with a cesarean section is twice that of a vaginal birth. The mother has every right to choose her method of delivery, but the obstetrician-gynecologist must explain all the benefits of vaginal birth before signing an agreement to perform a cesarean section without absolute medical indications. In general, women who choose a cesarean section do so because of fear of labor contractions, psychological trauma resulting from problems that arose during natural childbirth in their family or among friends, or family/professional pressure where the mode of delivery was agreed upon in advance. The fact that a cesarean section is not the preferred method in most cases does not mean that it does not offer certain advantages over vaginal delivery. Nevertheless, in cases where there are no medical indications, these benefits do not outweigh the risks associated with subjecting the mother to a surgical procedure. The benefits and conveniences offered by a cesarean section include:

- The ability to choose the exact date of birth in advance.
- Helps reduce maternal stress during childbirth by providing a sense of a fully controlled environment where everything is planned in advance.
- Childbirth is short and of expected duration.
- Ensures that the pregnant woman's obstetrician-gynecologist will be available on the day of delivery.
- Prevents post-term pregnancy (more than 42 weeks of gestation), which is associated with a higher risk of health problems in the newborn.
- Eliminates the risk of complications associated with the natural childbirth process, such as brachial plexus injury [4].

However, despite the positive aspects of a cesarean section, one should not overlook the negative aspects of this method of childbirth.

When a pregnant woman undergoes a cesarean section, she ceases to be simply a woman in labor and becomes a surgical patient. Thus, in addition to the potential risks inherent in any childbirth, the risks associated with any major surgery are also added. Here are some of the risks: the possibility of infection, injury during surgery, blood clots, hysterectomy, much longer-lasting pain, a longer hospital stay, and much more time needed to recover after childbirth. Infants are at greater risk of surgical cuts, breathing problems, and breastfeeding difficulties, and even childhood asthma and diabetes. Furthermore, nine out of ten women who have had a cesarean section in

the past will have another one. Repeated cesarean sections carry additional risks.

Complications for the mother include:

- Increased risk of infections.
- Increased risk of deep vein thrombosis.
- Increased risk of bleeding.
- Increased risk of reactions to anesthetics.
- Longer recovery time after childbirth.
- Higher incidence of postoperative pain.

The global maternal mortality rate is approximately 2.2 per 100,000 cesarean sections. Although this rate is low overall, it is significantly higher than for vaginal deliveries. The maternal mortality rate for vaginal deliveries is approximately 0.2 per 100,000 [4].

Conclusion

Cesarean section is becoming a common method of childbirth because it offers many advantages over natural childbirth. However, one must consider whether all these benefits are worth the potential complications that may arise following the procedure. According to the information provided earlier, if there are no absolute or relative indications for a cesarean section, natural childbirth is safer because the mechanism for it was designed by nature, and as psychosomatic specialists say, “the uterus is a very vengeful organ; it remembers everything and will surely take revenge for all the interventions caused when the time comes.”

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